

Geomorphology in the Digital Age: A Case Study Project of Quantitative Geomorphology from Images

Anselme Muzirafuti
dept. Mathematics, Informatics, Physics
and Earth Sciences
University of Messina
Messina, Italy
anselme.muzirafuti@unime.it

Giancarlo Faina
CoReMa Spiagge srl, Bologna, Italy
gfaina2@gmail.com

Stefania Lanza
Geologis srl
Messina, Italy
stefania.lanza@unime.it

Mohammed El Hafyani
Moulay Ismail University, Morocco
m.elhafyani@edu.umi.ac.ma

Diego Paltrinieri
CoReMa Spiagge srl, Bologna, Italy
dpaltrinieri59@gmail.com

Giovanni Randazzo
dept. Mathematics, Informatics, Physics
and Earth Sciences
University of Messina
Messina, Italy
giovanni.randazzo@unime.it

Abstract—In this paper we present the framework, data description, and main steps involved in the implementation of monitoring and forecasting systems aiming at the quantitative geomorphology of coastal areas. We demonstrate that such an objective can be achieved by considering current advanced technologies in Earth Observation and in remote sensing related research fields which provide the amount of data containing information on different geomorphological processes and landforms. Interpretation and analyses of these data into a Geographic information system (GIS) environment and the ability to share, visualize and store the results using the internet, allows for the implementation of monitoring and forecasting system through WebGIS necessary for product display and infrastructures at-risk assessment.

Keywords—UAV, photogrammetry, LiDAR, Remote sensing, machine learning, Land cover/land use, robotics, drone, satellite, WebGIS

I. INTRODUCTION

Globally, natural ecosystems are being affected by the current changes in climate [1]. The effects have been observed on littoral territories of coastal areas in the Mediterranean and low-laying regions in general [2]. In Italy, discussions related to the mitigation of hydrogeological risks, the protection of nature, and biodiversity have been the dominant subject for geoscientists [3]. Recently, several funding instruments for research activities have been adopted, primary for recovering from the effects of Covid-19 but also for promoting cohesion and sustaining regional development. In this case, the need to create networks for monitoring in support of planning which could counter the effects of territorial instability linked to the effects of Climate Change is essential. However, such tasks require an advanced and integrated monitoring and forecasting system [4]. In Sicily, to overcome hydrogeological territory instabilities we must move on from the current management tools to a dynamic planning system that is strongly interconnected between local administrations and central government [5]. In this sense, the Regional Plan Against Coastal Erosion has been drafted and approved as a scientific management tool taking into consideration geomorphological and sedimentological aspects [6]. Based on the know-how acquired during the pocket Beach Management and Remote Surveillance System (BESS) (Interreg Italia

Malta) project [5] we proposed the “Quantitative Geomorphology from Images” project.

The main objectives and the purpose of this project is to harness the latest remote sensing technological advancement in Robotics, platforms (Satellite and drones), geologic mapping, and Artificial intelligence (Machine learning algorithms) (Figs. 1, 2, 3), (Tabs. I, II) and develop coastal monitoring tools that are crucial for studying climate change impacts in low laying ecosystems territories. In this way, we proposed mathematical models useful for (1) satellite-derived bathymetry mapping, (2) shoreline forecasting, (3) sediment volume estimation, and (4) infrastructure-at-risk assessment studies.

TABLE I. SENSORS DESCRIPTIONS

Advanced Sensors	Bands used and sensor characteristics
Sentinel 2 MSI For 4 bands of 10 m of spatial resolution	B2 458-523 (nm) Blue B3 543-578 (nm) Green B4 650-680 (nm) Red B10 785-900 (nm) NIR
Landsat 8, 9 OLI For 4 bands of 30 m of spatial resolution	B2 450-510 (nm) Blue B3 530-590 (nm) Green B4 640-670 (nm) Red B5 850-880 (nm) NIR
Mavic 2 Pro	Hasselblad camera with 3 bands (RGB)
GNSS TOPCON Hiper HR receiver	Differential global positioning system
LiDAR Zenmuse L1	High precision IMU, Mid70 LiDAR Sensor, Visual assistant camera, 1 inch CMOS camera (45 Mpix), 3 Axis Gimbal
Single beam Echosounder	DGPS Garmin CSX 60 signal differential WAAS EGNOA

Fig. 1. Example of satellites and aerial imageries acquired on the beach of Noto pizzuta/Siracusa (SE of Sicily)

Fig. 2. Example of geologic (a), bathymetric (b) and shoreline (c) maps acquired on the beach of San Vito Lo Capo (NW of Sicily)

Fig. 3. Example of topo-bathymetric map (a), profile sections (b) and sediment excavation area (c) acquired on the beach of San Montano located on the Island of Ischia in the Gulf of Naples.

The project is conducted particularly by focusing on: (1) Machine learning for land cover/land use (LCLU) mapping, (2) Machine learning applied to photogrammetry and LiDAR technologies for 3D landform modelling, (3) Data fusion approaches applied to shoreline mapping and forecasting, and (4) Data fusion approaches applied to sedimentological mapping. These topics are related to some general objectives which concern: (A) the strengthening of the forecasting capacity of the effects of climate change through advanced and integrated monitoring and analysis systems, (B) the prevention and contrast of the consequences of climate change on hydrogeological instability phenomena and vulnerability of the territory, (C) the safeguarding of the territory through the protection of green areas, soil, and marine areas.

This research project was financed in the framework of Recovery Assistance for Cohesion and the Territories of Europe (REACT-EU) by the Italian National Operational Program "PON Research and Innovation 2014-2020" in innovation and green issues projects (DM 1062/2021). The project is related to a green thematic and was conceived on the basics that allows all the merits of the Next Generation EU research projects that are related to the National Recovery and Resilience Plan with a specific subject related to the protection of the territory, water resources, and to shoreline dynamic analyses (hot spots and rates of change points identification, and time series chart representations).

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

1) Project framework and Dataset Description:

Quantitative Geomorphological models and procedures adopted (Fig. 4) in the current project fit into: (A) the BESS project line of research. In this project we propose the aspects related to territorial monitoring by using the existing network

and by implementing coastal monitoring activities using data acquired via satellites and drones and by conducting analytical processing to promptly identify possible risks and their related impacts on systems and consequently define the optimal responses.

Fig. 4. Procedures and Quantitative Geomorphological models for Images analyses flowchart

The current project falls into (B) the National Smart Specialization Strategy [7], which identifies the long-term investment priorities shared with the Regions and the main stakeholders. Such investment ensures complementarity between the actions envisaged at the central level and those at the territorial level. Quantitative geomorphology from images project tackles objectives related to Blue Growth [8] in the sense that the production and the use of innovative of environmentally friendly materials such as the Relict Deep-Sea Sediments are crucial for the contrast of coastal erosion. In addition, this project explores aspects related to intelligence, safeguards, and community inclusiveness. Such an aspect is based on the fact that security and monitoring of the territory are fundamental for the defense against instability and for the sustainable use of the environments in which we live.

TABLE II. QUANTITATIVE GEOMORPHOLOGIC IMAGE ANALSES

Advanced Sensors	Analyzed parameters	Machine learning algorithms	Results
Sentinel 2 MSI	Bathymetry, Shoreline, bio-physical parameters	OBRA, SVM, Kalman Filter Model	SDB, LCLU, Shoreline position forecast,
Landsat 8, 9 OLI	Bathymetry, Shoreline, bio-physical parameters	OBRA, SVM, Kalman Filter Model	SDB, LCLU Shoreline position forecast,
Mavic 2 Pro	Shoreline, bio-physical parameters	Kalman Filter Model, SVM	Shoreline position forecast, LCLU, DEM, DSM
GNSS TOPCON Hiper HR receiver	Topography	RTK	Geographic coordinates
LiDAR Zenmuse L1	Topography	3D (DEM, DSM) models	Erosion and deposition volume
Single beam Echosounder	Bathymetry	3D model	Water depth and sediment volume

This project fits into (C) National Research Program trajectories such as thematic areas of smart and sustainable industry, energy, and environment. Here, a particular reference to the European and international dimension of research taking into account regional initiatives, contributions, and realities are considered;

Our project also fits falls into **(D)** National and International High-Profile Scientific Initiatives with reference to the adaptation of : (1) active and passive remote sensing techniques, such as liDAR technique (Figs. 5, 6); (2) GNSS framework and monitoring networks; (3) interpretation of digital images (satellite, drones); (4) modeling and monitoring of the territory; (5) LCLU mapping; and (6) environmental emergency situations management; in Universities researches and companies activities.

Fig. 5. LiDAR coloring point clouds using RGB acquired on the beach of Tono (NE of Sicily)

Fig. 6. LiDAR Coloring point clouds by height acquired on the beach of Tono (NE of Sicily)

2) Modules implementation:

2.1. Coastal sand beach volume changes estimation

The project takes advantages of the amount of freely available satellite imagery, such as those from Copernicus sentinel and Landsat programs to estimate (1) shoreline displacement and its displacement rate, surface variation, and annual sediments budget variation [9]. This is conducted by considering coastal sand beach area as a triangular prism (Fig. 9) and compute changes in sediment volume (Eq.1) by considering length of morphological sector (**L**), the shoreline displacement (**X**) (erosion or accretion) estimated from one transect and the depth of closure (**Y**) [9].

Fig. 7. Sand beach volume change estimation modelling

In our case, information on these variables (**L**, **X**) are extracted from imageries acquired by advanced sensors aboard of Sentinel-2, Landsat 8, 9 and Mavic 2 Pro, while the dept of closure can be estimated from equation 2.

$$V = L \frac{X \cdot Y}{2} \quad (1)$$

$$DoC = 2.28Hs - 68.5 \frac{Hs^2}{gT^2} \quad [10, 11] \quad (2)$$

where Hs equals to effective wave height exceeding 12 h per year, T equals to its associated period and g equals to gravity acceleration.

2.2. Kalman Filter framework for shoreline forecasting

Dynamics in shoreline positions can be evaluated by analyzing optic and active remote sensed imageries. This is achieved by computing shoreline change parameters such as **(1)** Net shoreline movement (**NSM**) which indicates the distance between the oldest and the youngest shoreline considered during the case study and for each transect; **(2)** End point rate (**EPR**) which indicates the rate of change between the oldest and the youngest shoreline for each transect **(3)**; Shoreline change envelope (**SCE**) which indicates the greatest distance among all the shorelines that intersect a given transect [12]. These analyses can be conducted in GIS environment using digital shoreline analysis system (DSAS) [13]. DSAS computes rate-of-change statistics for a time series of shoreline vectors (in shapefile format) obtained from different data sources (satellite images, UAV orthophoto, aerial images, cartographic maps or DSM, DEM). They provide useful information on shoreline displacement and its displacement rate, surface variation, and annual sediments budget variation. In addition, the estimation of Linear regression rate (Fig. 8) provides information necessary for future prediction and forecast of the shoreline position. The Kalman Filter model is often used for this operation, the algorithm provides quantitative statistical estimates of combined model-data forecast uncertainty [14]. This information is of great interest for conducting coastal hazard vulnerability assessments and future scenarios. The model is incorporated in DSAS and it can be estimated by computing the linear regression rate (**LRR**) (Fig.8), (Eq. 3). LRR is estimated by fitting a least-squared regression line to all shoreline points of a transect. It represents the change in meter per year (m/yr) that occurred on each transect. In this case, all the data are used, regardless of changes in trend or accuracy. In addition, it is possible to determine the coefficient of the determination (**LR²**) or the R-squared statistic (**R²**) which reflects the linear relationship between the shoreline points along a given DSAS transect.

$$Y = AX + B \quad (3)$$

Where Y is the predicted shoreline change, A is the linear regression rate, X is the time and B is the constant.

Fig. 8. Linear regression rate estimation (LRR): modified from [13], with shoreline dataset (baseline, transect, and shorelines and intersects) to describe the relationship between time and space data. The slope (A) of the equation describing the line is the rate.

2.3. Support Vector Machine for LCLU

The modification of the earth's surface by human activities drives the changes in LCLU [15]. Recently, remote sensing imageries played a critical role in the study of LCLU. This data can be used to identify and monitor LCLU over time [16,17] and at various scales. This is particularly useful for tracking changes in vulnerable and remote areas and identifying infrastructures at risk. By analyzing the spectral characteristics of different land cover types, LCLU mapping provides information on different bio-physical parameters, such as vegetation, water, bare land, and urban areas.

The analysis of remote sensing data has been revolutionized by the integration of machine learning algorithms such as artificial neural networks, decision trees, random forests, and support vectors machine (SVM) [18]. These algorithms have been used to classify and analyze large volumes of data, which would be too time-consuming or impossible for manual analysis [19].

SVM is a powerful machine learning algorithm that has been widely applied in the field of land use land cover change analysis [20, 16]. This algorithm has been used for both classification and prediction tasks and has been proven to be effective in identifying and mapping land cover changes over time [21]. By utilizing various data sources, such as UAV aerial photographs, satellites images, and ground truth data, SVM can accurately classify LCLU these remote sensed imageries into different categories, such as forest, urban, agriculture, and water (Fig.9).

Fig. 9. LCLU mapping of UAV aerial photograph with machine learning algorithm

2.4. Shoreline extraction indexing methods (NDVI, NDWI, thresholding)

The shoreline represents one of the most dynamic geomorphological features in coastal environments, due to natural and anthropogenic phenomena [2]. These changes are recorded over a long time, in the space of a few days or even a few hours. Such displacements, retreat or advance, are naturally accompanied by changes in sediment budget in a given littoral cell. This temporal differentiation allows us to understand how an ecosystem reacts to the effects of both anthropogenic and natural events. With the proliferation and advances in environment sensing technologies, seasonal and annual coastal evolution can be recorded and analyzed at various scales allowing to conduct a comparison of historical cartographic shoreline dynamics [22]. In our case, three methods (normalized difference vegetation index, normalized difference water index and, thresholding values) [23-25] were adopted to map and extract shoreline positions on optic imageries and then analyzed in the Esri Geographic Information System (ArcGIS) software using The DSAS 4.3.

$$NDVI = \frac{(NIR-R)}{(NIR+R)} \quad [23, 24] \quad (4)$$

$$NDWI = \frac{(G-NIR)}{(G+NIR)} \quad [25] \quad (5)$$

Usually, instantaneous shoreline can be obtained from remote sensed data, such shoreline should be corrected and transformed to the fixed shorelines (mean sea level shoreline) by considering the effects wave runup, tide and water-level anomalies (which could be obtained from wave buoy, tide gauge and datum measurements).

2.5. Satellite derived bathymetry (OBRA) method

The depth of shallow water information can be extracted remotely by analyzing bottom reflectance recorded by sensors in visible and near-infrared parties of the electromagnetic spectrum. On multispectral satellite images, bathymetry mapping can be conducted by exploring the reflectance registered in green and blue bands [26-28]. However, it is important to note that such methodology is applied in conjunction with limited in situ-data for calibration and the validation of the model.

$$SDB = m1 \frac{\ln(nRw(\lambda_i))}{\ln(nRw(\lambda_j))} - m0 \quad [26] \quad (6)$$

where (SDB) is satellite-derived bathymetry for shallow water that is usually limited to 30m in clear water and calm environment conditions. Rw (dimensionless) is observed spectral reflectance, for the n -factor we can use any positive number large enough that for all the pixels in the image both the logarithms used in the ratio are positive, $m0$ is the offset for the depth of 0 m ($z = 0$, y -axis intercept), λ_i is the blue band, and λ_j is the green band.

2. 6. Single beam echosounder for Bathymetric mapping

In addition to SDB, single beam echosounder is used for bathymetric survey of shallow and deep water. This is because SDB provides information on water no deeper than 30 m and with ideal environmental conditions. Therefore, the single beam echosounder (SBES) technique is a fundamental technique for measuring the depth of submerged surfaces.

This technique is based on a principle of normal reflection of an acoustic signal produced by a transducer placed on the surface of the water which travels the water column and once encounters the surface of the sea floor, it reflects and re-crosses the water column in the opposite direction and intercepted by a geophone placed next to the transducer. The measurement of the travel time between direct and reflected waves is returned as the distance of the source (transducer) from the seabed, which is skimmed by the transducer, and tide draft represents the depth.

To acquire morphological information of the seabed the system needed to be calibrated and synchronized with each component [29]. The SBES system is composed of (1) surface positioning system (DGPS, RTK, optical systems); (2) hydrographic depth sounder; (3) wave compensator for the correction of the depths detected in relation to the wave motion; (4) data acquisition and processing system consisting of dedicated hardware and software; (5) inertial system for evaluating the attitude of the boat and for correcting the depths detected according to the rolling and pitching movements of the echo sounder transducer; (6) Conductivity/Salinity Temperature Depth (CTD/STD) probe to measure the speed of sound in water [30]. The measurements are conducted following a predefined path with a vehicle running at low speed, on (1) lines perpendicular to the shoreline, and (2) cross lines parallel to the shoreline. Interpolation methods [31,32] are generally used to reconstruct the three-dimensional surface (Digital elevation Model) of the detected seabed. DEM with 5 m spatial resolution is elaborated using the Kriging interpolation method. Such DEM is used for the creation of the isobaths expressing the variation of water depth on bathymetric maps representing the variations in the morphology of the seabed, the deposition or erosion of sediments.

2.7. Digital elevation and surface models (DEM, DSM)

Aerial photogrammetry, LiDAR technique and in-situ measurement are used to generate DEM and DSM. In this context, GNSS TOPCON Hiper HR receiver, LiDAR Zenmuse L1, and Mavic 2 Pro drone are used to conduct topographic surveys. The use of these tools allows to take very high-definition photographs (with Mavic 2 Pro), Point cloud (with LiDAR) and geographic coordinates (with GNSS TOPCON Hiper HR receiver) of coastal areas [33]. The Mavic 2 Pro is equipped with an integrated GPS for positioning and IMU inertial platform with 3 accelerometers and 3 gyroscopes capable of instantly calculating the position, speed, and drift of the vehicle in flight. The aircraft system also consists of a 2.4 GHz radio control piloting system and a control unit for the management of missions sent from a

ground control station; the control station sends the data to the UAV with a 2.4 GHz UHF Data Telemetry system and the AUV system sends the images in real-time with a 5.8 GHz Video Telemetry system. The LiDAR system is composed of an integrated LiDAR module, RGB camera, High accuracy IMU (0.025° roll/pitch, 0.08° yaw) IP54 Ingress protect Level for water protection, High point rate (24000 pts/sec), High vertical (5cm) and horizontal (10 cm) accuracies, the system support 3 return with a high efficiency survey covering 2 km² in single flight and for a detection range of about 450 m. The acquired data are processed in GIS environment with different software such as (PiX4D, Spatix, DJI Terra, ArcMap, Qgis...) for quantitative geomorphological analyses useful for shoreline dynamic analyses (hot spots and rates of change points identification, time series chart representations).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Advanced and integrated monitoring and forecasting system.

The present geomorphology in the Digital Age Case Study Project falls in the scope of image analyses concept main purpose of extracting information needed for quantitative geomorphology of landform, geological processes, and natural and anthropological phenomenon and their effects on the landscape. In this proposed project, we demonstrate that such objectives can be achieved by adopting the current advanced technologies in Earth Observation and in remote sensing related research fields. Interpretation and analyses of imageries acquired through these technologies in Geographic information system (GIS) environment particularly using DSAS for rate-of-change statistics analysis and shoreline forecasting, or by using machine learning algorithms and topographic modelling for sediment volume estimation or for infrastructure at-risk assessment. We also noticed that digital terrain model of seabed can be studied by using satellite images for shallow water or single beam echosounder for shallow and relatively deep water. By taking into account the current technology into data sharing, visualization and storage using internet, we noticed that monitoring and forecasting system can be implemented through WebGIS development and product display (Fig. 10).

Input	Data processing	Output	WebGIS development and product display
Multiple L8, S2 images	NDVI, NDWI, Thresholding	Shoreline, Baseline, Transsects	Rate and maps of changes, Shoreline forecasting
Aerial photograph	SDB	Bathymetry	Water depth
Single L8, S2 image	SVM	LCLU estimation	Infrastructures at risk
Aerial photograph, Single L8, S2 image	DEM, DSM modelling	Watershed, Topographic maps, Drainage and slope maps, TIN and shaded relief	Sediment volume estimation, Relief visualization, Hydrology
Single Beam Echosounder	Interpolation	Bathymetry	Water depth
Geologic map	Digitization	Geologic units	Sediment and rock types

Fig. 10. Main steps involved in monitoring and forecasting system implementation.

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